

Relationship between Mandala Art and Emotional Intelligence among Undergraduate Students: An Intervention

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Emotional Intelligence plays a crucial role in understanding emotions, managing relations, and maintaining psychological well-being (Salove & Mayer, 1990). This present study was conducted to explore the relationship between mandala art therapy and emotional intelligence among undergraduate students. This present study used a pre-test and post-test mixed-method research design using a convenience sampling method. Total of six participants took part in a Mandala Art Therapy Intervention, which was designed to explore emotions of the individual and assist in mindfulness, emotional expression, and self-reflection through structured mandala creation and colouring activity. Emotional Intelligence was examined across 10 factors of Emotional Intelligence: Self-awareness, empathy, self-motivation, emotional stability, managing relations, integrity, self-development, value orientation, commitment, and altruistic behavior. The collected data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and a paired sample t-test to examine the significant difference between pre-test and post-test scores. The results showed an overall improvement in emotional intelligence following the intervention. The mean score of overall emotional intelligence increased from 75.67 (pre-test) to 82.5 (Post-test). Statistical analysis also showed a significant improvement in the overall emotional intelligence scores. In addition to the quantitative findings, participants' subjective feedback suggested that the mandala art creation and colouring process created a sense of calmness, emotional awareness, and mindfulness. Many Participants described the experience of relaxation, while some also reported deeper emotional exploration during the mandala creation and colouring process. Overall findings suggest that Mandala Art Therapy can be useful as a creative and expressive tool for improving emotional intelligence and promoting emotional awareness. This present study highlights the potential of using art-based therapeutic practices in educational as well as psychological settings.

Keywords: Emotional intelligence, mandala art therapy, art therapy, emotional awareness

Mandala is a Sanskrit word that means 'Circle'. Mandala Art also represents or is used as the symbol of 'Universe', 'Self Awareness', 'Spiritual Growth', and 'Balance and Harmony' (Twinkl, n.d.). From ancient times, it has had a complex, symmetrical, and geometrical configuration as a symbol in various cultures. Mandala Art is being used in Hinduism, Buddhism, Islam, Christianity and Native Americans (Kalatman, 2023). In Native Americans use it for healing and vision quests like Navajo sand paintings. In Mandala, each shape and pattern has a spiritual meaning. Mandala can be used in daily life for the purpose of relaxation, meditation, stress reduction, to express emotions, and to be mindful (Kalatman, 2023). Carl Jung, the famous Swiss psychiatrist, was the first person to introduce the Mandala Art in the area of psychological well-being. Jung believed that the mandala represents the 'Self', which means pure personality and the mandala is an 'Archetypes of wholeness'. He also observed

that mandala art reflects the person's inner state and progress (Butler, 2015). According to Jung, a mandala is a psychological map that allows individuals to explore the unconscious mind and he observed, patient who created the mandala art, they often expressed the need for wholeness, harmony, and inner balance (MandalaGenius, 2025).

Figure 1

Easy Mandala Coloring Page for Adults and Kids, " n.d.

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Mayer and Salovey (1990) were the first researchers to discover the concept of Emotional Intelligence. Emotional Intelligence is the subset of social intelligence in which a person can understand, recognize, and analyze their own and others' emotions and guide their thinking and behaviour (Explore Psychology Staff, 2019). According to Goldman (1995), emotional competencies are: - (a) Self-Awareness: - the ability to understand one's own feelings and how it affects others. (b) Social Skills: - ability to interact well with other people and understanding, managing, and expressing emotions. (c) Self-regulation: - ability to manage and regulate

emotions in a healthy and acceptable way. (d) Motivation: - the ability for perusing things that are beyond the external rewards to fulfil their own needs and goals. (e) Empathy: - the ability to understand others' feelings by putting oneself in that position. It can influence how a person responds to others when dealing with difficult emotions. "Emotional intelligence is the ability to track one's own and others' emotions and to discriminate among them and to use this information to help and guide one's thinking and actions in constructive and positive ways" (Hyde, Pethe, & Dhar, 2002).

Review of Literature

Bakshi et al. (2019) aimed to see the effect of mandala art therapy on Functional social skills and attention among intellectually disabled children. The sample size was 32 intellectually disabled children and pre-post design was used. After four-week intervention of coloring pre-drawn mandala, significant improvements in social skills, attention, and vocational skills were seen. Study concluded that Mandala art therapy can be a useful technique for enhancement of social functioning and attention in intellectually disabled children. Shah et al. (2021) used pre post design, with a sample of 56 participants. The study assessed the effect of mandala art on psychological well-being of physiotherapy undergraduate students between the age of 18-22 years old. Their findings revealed that coloring or drawing mandala art can lead to significant reductions in psychological distress, and also suggested that this art-based intervention can be effective for enhancing emotional well-being among undergraduate physiotherapy students. T M et al. (2024) assessed the effect of Mandala art on mental health by using a pre-post design with sample size of 30 participants and evaluated the changes in the level of stress, anxiety, depression, and resilience. Findings explained that mandala art therapy has a significant impact on the reduction of symptoms of stress, anxiety, and depression and showed enhancement in resilience in participants. Result highlighted Mandala art intervention as a supportive strategy for mental health in university students. In Conclusion, according to all five non-indian studies, mandala art therapy consistently demonstrates meaningful psychological, emotional, and behavioral benefits across diverse populations-including children with intellectual disabilities, high school and university students, and individuals undergoing alcohol de-addiction treatment. The mandala intervention has been shown to reduce stress, psychological distress, anxiety, depression, and withdrawal symptoms, while enhancing attention, emotional well-being, social functioning, and resilience. The evidence suggests that mandala art therapy is a low-cost, versatile, and effective supportive intervention that promotes mental health and overall well-being in both clinical and non-clinical groups.

Gürçan et al. (2021) aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of individual mandala drawing methods on psychological symptoms, anxiety and depression in hospitalized adolescents with cancer, with a pre-post study and a sample size of 60 adolescents (ages 12-17). Samples were randomly assigned to two groups: the intervention group, which completed 12-hour mandala drawing sessions and the control group, which received routine care. Assessment was measured at baseline and after 5 days of intervention. Results showed a significant reduction in anxiety, depression, and psychological symptoms in adolescents who participated in mandala drawing compared to the control group. This concludes that mandala drawing is an effective and supportive tool for improving emotional

and psychological well-being in adolescents with undergoing cancer treatment. Khademi et al. (2021) used a pre-post design with a sample size of 70. This randomized controlled clinical trial helped to examine the effect of mandala coloring on anxiety in hospitalized COVID-19 patients. An intervention group was receiving the mandala coloring sessions for 30 minutes daily over 6 days, while the control group was receiving the standard care only. At the start, both the intervention and control groups had similar levels of anxiety but after the intervention, the intervention group showed a significant reduction in anxiety level compared to the control group. Results indicate that daily practicing the mandala coloring is an effective and supportive method for reducing anxiety in hospitalized COVID-19 patients and also may serve as a useful tool for routine care. Salazar et al. (2019) used a quasi experimental design with a sample size of 106 students. This study explored whether mandala coloring can reduce math anxiety among undergraduate business students results showed that math anxiety can be significantly reduced by coloring a pre-drawn mandala as compared to a doodling control group. Additionally, analysis of this study also revealed that anxiety reduction in male students is greater than in females after coloring the mandala. In Conclusion, across various age groups and settings-including COVID-19 units, cancer wards, universities, and families of children with special needs-mandala art therapy consistently reduces anxiety, negative mood, and psychological distress, while enhancing comfort, mindfulness, resilience, and emotional well-being. Both coloring and creating mandala drawings show therapeutic value, with unstructured creation encouraging deeper emotional expression. Together, these studies strongly support mandala art therapy as an accessible, versatile, and effective intervention for improving mental health and emotional health in both clinical and non-clinical populations.

Kant (2019/2025) assessed the level of emotional intelligence (EI) with sample size of 200 students (the Central University of South Bihar, Gaya, India) and analyzed differences based on locality, gender, level of course, and school of study using a survey method. The findings revealed that students from the school of education scored a high level of emotional intelligence compared to students from the school of law and governance. Also, a significant gender difference was observed; female students scored higher in emotional intelligence than male students. No significant difference was found between undergraduate and postgraduate students, although undergraduates showed slightly higher mean EI scores. The locality of students did not have a significant impact on emotional intelligence, but students from rural backgrounds exhibited higher mean EI levels compared to urban students. Pande (2021) focused on comparing emotional intelligence (EI) levels among 80 students enrolled in specialized fields at Gondwana University. By using simple random sampling, 20 students each from Commerce, Science, Social Work, and Law departments were selected and emotional intelligence was measured using a standardized EI scale. Using one-way ANOVA followed by post hoc tests, data were analyzed where significant differences were found. Results showed a significant difference in overall emotional intelligence among students from four academic disciplines and significant differences were observed across various emotional intelligence factors suggesting that students' fields of study influence their emotional intelligence levels. In conclusion, University students generally have average to high levels of emotional intelligence (EI), but this is influenced by factors such as

gender, field of study, and disability status. Academic discipline influences EI levels, while the effect of gender is mixed, and the difference between undergraduate and postgraduate students is insignificant. These findings highlight the need for targeted strategies to promote emotional development and encourage inclusivity in higher education.

Williams et al. (2014) assessed the level of empathy among law graduate students and to assess this, the Jefferson Scale of Empathy was adapted to the legal context. The Revised Jefferson Scale of Empathy-Law Students (JSE-L-S) was administered to 275 students at Monash University, Australia, and the data were analyzed using principal component analysis. The analysis identified four factors related to empathy: understanding the customer's perspective, responding to customers' experiences and emotions, responding to customers' cues and behaviors, and understanding customers' situations. These factors explained 46.7% of the total variance. This composite scale, consisting of 18 items, demonstrated good reliability with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.80 and showed a pattern consistent with other versions of the Jefferson Scale of Empathy. The study concludes that the JSE-L-S method is a reliable tool for measuring empathy in students and may be useful in understanding their well-being and future professional performance. Further refinement and evaluation are recommended to enhance its psychometric properties. Shengyao et al. (2024) studied 518 Chinese university students, and emotional intelligence was found to be positively related to psychological well-being and academic achievement, in which self-efficacy, motivation and resilience were acting as the key mediators. This effect was stronger in postgraduate students, suggesting that enhancing emotional intelligence and coping skills can improve both mental well-being and academic performance. In Conclusion, Emotional intelligence (EI) and its related abilities-empathy, creativity, and spiritual well-being-are crucial for personal, academic, and professional success. Reliably measured empathy in law students promotes well-being and future professional performance. EI positively influences psychological well-being, academic achievement, and qualities such as self-efficacy, motivation, and resilience, especially in postgraduate students. Creativity, life satisfaction, and emotional awareness also predict academic success, which highlights the need to integrate these skills into higher education. In business settings, EI enhances leadership, team collaboration, conflict resolution, and motivation. Overall, developing EI along with creativity and empathy improves individual performance and organizational outcomes, thereby supporting EI-focused interventions in education and workplaces.

Singh et al. (2023) evaluated the effects of mandala coloring on children aged 6-10 years with ADHD symptoms. A total of 120 children were divided into two groups: An intervention group, which practiced mandala coloring for 10 weeks, and a control group. Pre- and post-tests measured executive functioning and emotional and motivational self-regulation (EMSRQ). Results showed that executive functioning improved significantly in the intervention group, while there was no significant change in the EMSRQ. Parents also reported increased academic performance, concentration, and the ability to focus on tasks for longer periods of time. The study concluded that mandala coloring is a simple and effective technique for improving attention span and cognitive abilities in children at risk for ADHD, which can be easily implemented at home. Further research is needed to compare its effectiveness with other interventions. S. K. et al. (2024) examined the effectiveness of

mandala art therapy in improving social anxiety, emotional regulation, and mental health in working professionals. Of the initial 239 participants, 53 (29 men, 24 women) were included in the before-after study without a control group. Social Interaction Anxiety Scale (SIAS-6), Social Phobia Scale (SPS-6), Emotional Regulation Questionnaire (ERQ) and Short Warwick Edinburgh Mental Health Scale (SWEMWB) were used for assessment. The results showed that social anxiety has a negative correlation with both emotional regulation and mental health, while emotional regulation has a positive correlation with mental health. The study concluded that mandala art therapy effectively reduces social anxiety and enhances emotional regulation and overall mental health. In Conclusion, Mandala-based healing methods, including coloring and art therapy, effectively improve concentration, emotional control, mental health, and stress management across different age groups. They improve executive functioning and academic performance in children with ADHD, reduce social anxiety in working professionals, promote emotional health, and encourage emotional regulation and healthy habits in teens facing academic stress. These treatments are simple, accessible, and beneficial, although further research is needed to assess their long-term effectiveness and compare them with other methods.

Faas et al. (2023) using frameworks from attachment theory and art therapy, examined the effects of coloring in pre-made mandalas on emotional regulation, awareness, and stateful attachment style in adults by a mixed-methods study. Participants completed a mandala coloring activity, with pre- and post-assessment using the State Adult Attachment Measure (SAAM), Emotion Regulation Questionnaire (ERQ), and qualitative interviews. Results showed that mandala coloring increased awareness, promoted adaptive emotional regulation, and led to initial improvements in attachment security. This study highlights the potential of low-risk, non-directive art-making interventions to improve psychological well-being, especially for adults who are hesitant to engage in traditional therapy. These findings support the use of mandala-based coloring as a therapeutic and preventative tool, which has implications for clinical practice and community mental health. In Conclusion, the reviewed studies suggest that mandala-based interventions ranging from coloring and mindful drawing to structured art therapy can enhance emotional regulation, awareness, concentration and socio-emotional abilities in different age groups. In adults, mandala coloring promotes adaptive emotional regulation and awareness and can improve attachment security. In preschool children, mindfulness-based mandala interventions improve concentration, emotion awareness, regulation, and social-emotional understanding. Evidence from patients suggests potential benefits in reducing stress, anxiety, pain, and improving hope and resilience, although the quality of current studies limits generalizability. Overall, mandala-based practices appear to be accessible, low-risk interventions that hold promise for promoting psychological well-being, but further high-quality research is needed to confirm their efficacy and long-term effects.

Rationale

As the population, Undergraduate students were selected because of 3 reasons: To have a specific population for the study, Undergraduate students experience a competitive environment, emotional stress and high academic pressure, Emotional Intelligence development is crucial at this stage, not only for academic adjustment but also for future professional effectiveness in the legal field.

To the best of the researcher's knowledge, research gap exists in the lack of intervention-based studies by using mandala art as a tool to enhance emotional intelligence, especially among undergraduate students. Apart from this, no known Indian study has assessed the relationship between mandala art and emotional intelligence within legal education. Addressing this gap, this present study aims to assess the relationship between mandala art and emotional intelligence through a structured intervention, culturally adaptable, offering a low cost, and psychologically-based approach to emotional skill development in undergraduate students.

Method

This present study was done with the objective of finding out the relationship between Mandala Art and Emotional Intelligence in undergraduate students. Hypothesis was constructed - There will be a significant positive relationship between Mandala Art Intervention and Emotional Intelligence in Undergraduate students.

Participants

A total of 6 participants were selected for the intervention (out of 40 age of 18-30 years) using Convenience Sampling has scored low to normal in emotional intelligence questionnaire as pre-test. Participants who were undergoing any psychological treatment or suffered from severe emotional or psychiatric conditions were excluded from this study.

Measure

Emotional Intelligence Scale developed by Hyde, Pethe, and Dhar (2002) was used to assess level of emotional intelligence among undergraduate students. This scale consists of 34 items which cover 10 factors of emotional intelligence - Emotional Intelligence factors as per the tool are Self-Awareness (A), Empathy(B), Self-Motivation (C), Emotional Stability (D), Managing Relations (E), Integrity (F), Self-Development (G), Value Orientation (H), Commitment (I), and Altruistic Behavior (J). Their responses were recorded on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from "Strongly agree" to "Strongly disagree". Highest scores represent greater emotional intelligence and lower scores indicate poor emotional intelligence. This tool also has good reliability ($\alpha = 0.88$) and high validity ($\alpha = 0.93$), which makes it suitable for the Indian context (Hyde, Pethe, & Dhar, 2002).

Statistical Analysis

Descriptive statistics were computed for all the study variables. The collected pre-test and post-test data was analyzed using a paired sample t-test to examine changes in emotional intelligence following the mandala art intervention.

Procedure

This present study has used a mixed method, pre-post-test intervention design within a group. Emotional Intelligence was assessed in undergraduate students before and after the 4-days Mandala Art Intervention to see the changes resulting from intervention and to explore the relationship between Mandala Art and Emotional Intelligence. The intervention consisted of a structured 4-day mandala art program conducted through group based online sessions, with one session per day lasting approximately 60-75 minutes. Each session included brief

relaxation and guided visualization focusing on specific emotions (Fear, Anger, sadness, & happiness), followed by a mandala creation and colouring activity to facilitate self-reflection and emotional expression. Participants were encouraged to focus on their thoughts, emotions, and bodily sensations during the creative process without concern for artistic ability. Emotional intelligence was assessed before and after the intervention using the same scale.

Results

This present section describes the findings of the present study with the help of a mixed method research design to assess the relationship between mandala art and emotional intelligence among undergraduate students. Quantitative analysis was done using pre-test and post-test emotional intelligence scores and qualitative analysis was done based on feedback given by the participants post-mandala intervention.

Quantitative Analysis

For quantitative analysis, statistical analysis was done using IBM SPSS Statistics and to compare the pre-intervention and post-intervention scores of the 6 participants, the paired sample t-test was applied.

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics

Domain Measures	Test	N	Mean	Standard Deviation
Self-Awareness (A)	Pre	6	8.67	0.52
	Post	6	9.17	1.83
Empathy(B)	Pre	6	11.17	1.17
	Post	6	12.17	0.98
Self-Motivation (C)	Pre	6	14.33	1.21
	Post	6	15.5	1.51
Emotional Stability(D)	Pre	6	8.5	1.05
	Post	6	8.83	1.47
Managing Relations (E)	Pre	6	8.83	1.17
	Post	6	9.83	1.47
Integrity(F)	Pre	6	6.33	0.82
	Post	6	6.5	0.84
Self-Development(G)	Pre	6	4	0.89
	Post	6	4.33	1.50
Value Orientation(H)	Pre	6	5	0.89
	Post	6	5.83	0.41
Commitment(I)	Pre	6	4.17	0.41
	Post	6	5	1.09
Altruistic Behaviour(J)	Pre	6	4.67	0.82
	Post	6	5.33	1.03
Overall Emotional Intelligence	Pre	6	75.67	4.55
	Post	6	82.5	7.06

Conclusion

The mean score of all factors of emotional intelligence in descriptive statistics indicates improvement from pre-test to post-test. This suggests that mandala art intervention was effective in enhancing various aspects of emotional intelligence among undergraduate students, including Self-awareness, empathy, self-motivation, emotional stability, managing relations, integrity, self-development, value orientation, commitment, and altruistic behavior.

Table 2*Paired Samples t-test*

Domain	Variable	t	df	One- sided p	Two-sided p
Self-Awareness (A)	Pre vs Post Test	-0.696	5	0.259	0.518
Empathy(B)	Pre vs Post Test	-1.936	5	0.055	0.111
Self-Motivation (C)	Pre vs Post Test	-2.445	5	0.029	0.058
Emotional Stability (D)	Pre vs Post Test	-0.791	5	0.233	0.465
Managing Relations (E)	Pre vs Post Test	-1.936	5	0.055	0.111
Integrity (F)	Pre vs Post Test	-0.415	5	0.348	0.695
Self-Development (G)	Pre vs Post Test	-0.791	5	0.233	0.465
Value Orientation (H)	Pre vs Post Test	-2.076	5	0.046	0.093
Commitment (I)	Pre vs Post Test	-2.076	5	0.046	0.093
Altruistic Behaviour (J)	Pre vs Post Test	-2	5	0.051	0.102
Overall Emotional Intelligence	Pre vs Post Test	-2.59	5	0.024	0.049

Note. Statistically significant at $p < 0.05$

Table 2 presents the paired sample t-test results to examine the difference between pre-test scores and post-test scores of various domains of emotional intelligence among the participants. The paired t-test is used to test whether the mean difference between two related groups (pre & post scores) is statistically significant. The table includes t-value, degrees of freedom, one-sided t-values and two-sided t-values.

Self-Awareness (A): The t-value is -0.696 with a two-sided p -value of 0.58. Since $p > 0.05$, the difference between pretest and posttest is not statistically significant.

Empathy (B): The t value is -1.936 with a two-sided p value of 0.111. The finding is not statistically significant at the 0.05 level. The one-sided p -value (0.055) shows that the result is close to significance level, which suggests a possible improvement in empathy after the intervention.

Self-Motivation (C): The t-value is -2.445 with a two-sided p -value of 0.058. Since the value is slightly higher than 0.05, which indicates that the result is not statistically significant at 0.05 level. The one-sided p -value is 0.029, which is less than 0.05 suggesting a statistically significant improvement in self-motivation when considering a directional hypothesis.

Emotional Stability (D): The t-value is -1.936 with a two-sided p -value of 0.111, which indicates that the difference between pre-test and post-test scores is not statistically significant because p -value is greater than 0.05.

Managing Relations (E): The t-value is -0.791 with a two-sided p -value of 0.465, which is higher than 0.05, which indicates no statistically significant difference.

Integrity (F): The t value is -0.415 with a two-sided p value of 0.695 which clearly indicates that there is no statistically significant difference between pre-test scores and post-test scores.

Self-Development (G): The t-value is -0.791 with a two-sided p -value of 0.465 ($p > 0.05$), which clearly indicates that there is no statistically significant difference between pre-test scores and post-test scores.

Value Orientation (H): The t-value is -2.076 with a two-sided p -value of 0.093. Since the p -value is greater than 0.05, this clearly indicates that there is no statistically significant difference between pre-test scores and post-test scores. The one-sided p -value is 0.046, which indicates a statistically significant improvement in value orientation.

Commitment (I): The t-value is -2.076 with a two-sided p -value of 0.093, which clearly indicates that there is no statistically significant difference between pre-test scores and post-test scores because $p > 0.05$ but the one-sided p -value is 0.046, which indicates a statistically significant improvement.

Altruistic Behaviour (J): The t value is -2 with a two-sided p -value of 0.102, which indicates that there is no statistically significant difference between pre-test scores and post test scores at 0.05 level because $p > 0.05$.

Overall Emotional Intelligence: For the overall emotional intelligence score, the t value is -2.29 with a two-sided p -value of 0.049; since $p < 0.05$, the result is statistically significant. Result shows that a significant difference was found between pre-test scores and post-test scores. This suggests that mandala art intervention had a positive and statistically significant effect on emotional intelligence among participants.

Conclusion: The paired sample t-test results show that even though most individual domains did not reach statistical significance at the 0.05 level in two-tailed test, several domains like Self-awareness, empathy, self-motivation, emotional stability, managing relations, integrity, self-development, value orientation, commitment, and altruistic behavior showed improvement.

Most importantly, the overall emotional intelligence score showed a statistically significant improvement after the mandala art intervention, which suggests that the mandala art intervention program was effective in enhancing the emotional intelligence of the participants.

Qualitative Analysis: For qualitative analysis, participants' subjective feedback was taken after the mandala art intervention in their own words. The feedback provided by the participants reflects their personal experiences of the mandala art workshop. Overall, the feedback shows that the mandala art workshop created a meaningful psychological and emotional experience for the participants. Most of the feedback shows feelings of calmness, emotional awareness, personal growth, and self-exploration, though one participant also reported some emotional discomfort during the process of the mandala art workshop. In Conclusion, all the feedback suggests that the mandala art intervention provided participants with the opportunity for emotional expression, self-exploration, mindfulness, and psychological relaxation. Most of the participants

experienced positive outcomes like satisfaction, peace, greater emotional awareness, and improved focus. At the same time, one participant highlighted that the process can also bring unconscious emotions to the surface, which is an important aspect of mandala art therapeutic intervention. Overall, the qualitative feedback indicates that the mandala art workshop was beneficial and meaningful for most of the participants.

Discussion

This present chapter describes the effectiveness of mandala art intervention in enhancing emotional intelligence among participants. The mandala art workshop was conducted to assess the impact of emotional intelligence using pre-test and post-test scores, which have various domains such as Self-awareness, empathy, self-motivation, emotional stability, managing relations, integrity, self-development, value orientation, commitment, and altruistic behavior.

The paired sample t-test analysis supported these findings. The result explained that the overall emotional intelligence score showed a significant difference between pre-test and post-test ($t = -2.59, p = 0.049$) because the p-value is less than 0.05. This suggests that the mandala art therapeutic intervention has a positive effect on enhancing emotional intelligence. Some of the individual domains, like self-awareness, value orientation, and commitment, showed near-significant improvements in one-sided p-value. Although all the domains did not reach a statistically significant difference in two-sided p-value, the consistent increase in mean scores indicates a positive trend in emotional intelligence development among participants. These findings are supported by the study of Shah and Borkar (2021) which also reported that mandala art intervention significantly reduced psychological distress, improve psychological well-being, and enhances emotional intelligence among undergraduate students. As improved emotional well-being is related to emotional awareness and regulation, which are factors of emotional intelligence. Therefore, both studies collectively suggest that mandala art intervention can help to improve emotional intelligence even if some factors show gradual improvements rather than immediate statistical significance.

The qualitative feedback obtained from participants further supported the quantitative findings of the study. Participants generally reported feelings of peace, emotional clarity, and relaxation during the process of drawing and coloring mandala art. Many described the repetitive patterns and intentional use of colors based on their emotions as helpful in maintaining present-moment awareness, thereby facilitating emotional expression and mindfulness. The creative process appeared to provide participants with a reflective space to observe and process their internal emotional experiences. Several participants described the workshop as a positive and meaningful experience. One participant reported that the use of colors in the mandala creation process evoked feelings of happiness and enjoyment. Another participant noted that the activity brought forward previously unconscious emotional material, particularly fears that surfaced in dreams and briefly affected sleep and concentration. Although this experience was somewhat uncomfortable, it suggests that mandala art may facilitate deeper psychological processing and the emergence of suppressed emotions. Other participants highlighted the novelty of the intervention and appreciated the safe and supportive environment it created for emotional exploration. Participants also reported

increased clarity, inner reflection, and improved productivity in the days following the sessions. Overall, the qualitative responses indicate that mandala art intervention may serve as a calming, reflective, and emotionally expressive activity that supports self-awareness and emotional processing among undergraduate students.

Conclusion

The present study aimed to explore the impact of mandala art therapy on emotional intelligence among undergraduate students. A mixed-method pretest-posttest design was used with a sample of six participants selected from an initial group of 40 students. Participants attended a four-day online mandala art therapy workshop. Emotional intelligence was assessed using a standardized scale measuring ten domains: self-awareness, empathy, self-motivation, emotional stability, managing relations, integrity, self-development, value orientation, commitment, and altruistic behavior. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and a paired-samples t-test. The results indicated an overall increase in emotional intelligence scores following the intervention, suggesting a significant improvement after participation in the mandala art workshop. Qualitative feedback from participants further indicated experiences of relaxation, mindfulness, and emotional reflection during the creative process. Overall, the findings suggest that mandala art therapy may serve as a useful creative and reflective approach for enhancing emotional awareness and emotional intelligence among undergraduate students.

Limitations of the Present Study

The sample size of this present study was small ($N=6$), which limits the generalizability of findings. The intervention duration was small (4 sessions only). The research was conducted with a specific group of participants and in an online setting.

Implications of the Study

Mandala Art therapy can be used as a psychological intervention to enhance emotional intelligence. Educational institutions can use creative art-based activities like mandala art to enhance the student's emotional intelligence development. Counselors and psychologists can use mandala drawing as a tool for stress management and emotional expression. Mandala art workshops can promote self-awareness, mindfulness, and creativity among individuals.

Suggestions and Future Research

Conduct research with a larger sample for improving the generalizability. Use a longer intervention period (more than 4) to observe the bigger emotional changes. Include a control group to strengthen the research design. Conduct longitudinal studies to examine the long-term effects of art therapy interventions like mandala art therapy.

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